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MONITORING WILD POLLINATORS IN THE ITALIAN NATIONAL
PARKS: SHARING METHODS AND DATA FOR EVALUATION
AT NATIONAL LEVEL

*Monitoraggio degli impollinatori selvatici nei parchi nazionali italiani:
condivisione di metodi e dati per la valutazione a livello nazionale*

In response to the European Habitats (92/43/EEC) and Birds (2009/147/EC) directives, Italy has identified a network of Sites of Community Interest (SIC)/ Special Conservation Area (SCA) and Special Protection Areas (ZPS) collectively called Natura 2000 network, which covers about 19 % of the national territory. However, these areas protected almost never have lists of their patrimony of invertebrates species ad exception, and for a minority of cases, of the better known groups such as some families of beetles, butterflies and dragonflies. Regarding the bees, cases of published lists (not exhaustive) concern only some Italian National Parks (e.g., Gran Paradiso, Tuscan Archipelago, Sibillini Mountains, Abruzzo, Circeo, Vesuvius). The proven presence of a species in a protected area can be essential for conservation. Therefore, it would be necessary both to encourage sampling within the protected areas by experts trained on the standardized methods and highlight the information relating to the presence of species in certainly protected areas.

The Directives of Ministry of the Environment, the Italian Ministry of the Environment (MITE), to favor an ecoregional system approaches among national parks (NP), since the 2019 financed the monitoring of wild pollinators, according to Habitat Directive and the European Pollinator Initiative. The monitoring objectives, general and specific, based on the requirements of the Directives of the Minister and the European Pollinators Initiative are: know the status and trend of pollinating insects; verify the effect of pressures resulting from agricultural activity, the use of plant protection products, graz-

ing, the degradation and disappearance of suitable habitats, climate change, the introduction of alien species, etc.; evaluate the effectiveness of measures for reducing impacts; define, if possible, the check list of the species present in the NP territory and their eventual inclusion in the National or European Red Lists of bees, butterflies and hoverflies (VAN SWAAY *et al.*, 2010; NIETO *et al.*, 2014; VUJI *et al.*, 2022).

Monitoring of pollinating insects through field surveys are carrying out on the territories of NP, following a new protocol defined by the National Institute of Environment Research and Protection (ISPRA) and University of Turin (D'ANTONI *et al.*, 2020). This protocol includes data collection of bees and butterflies (and if possible, hoverflies) richness and abundance, flora sampling, and covariates related to agricultural management and environment. To facilitate the collection of standardized data an APP was developed according to the EU-PoMS (POTTS *et al.*, 2020). The results are embedded in the central hub National Network Biodiversity (NNB).

The monitoring of pollinators also partly complies with article 17 of the Habitats Directive focused on capturing the status and trends of habitat types and species, considering that Italy counts 16 protected diurnal butterfly species of which at least two are very closely linked to agricultural habitats and at least nine occur in national parks.

Effective protection of native pollinators is critical (BALLETO *et al.*, 2015; QUARANTA *et al.*, 2018) so it is crucial to adopt measures to reserve areas for native pollinators in agroecosystems to provide resources and nesting sites for their conservation and, consequently, ensure the pollination ecosystem service. Edges, field margins, riparian forests, natural meadows, and pastures are relevant as places where native pollinators can thrive. The seriousness of their disappearance and the urgency of their conservation is worrying, so it was important to use the monitoring adopting techniques validated at the European level and applied uniformly to all NP areas to perform enormous progress in filling existing knowledge gaps (IUCN STANDARDS & PETITIONS COMMITTEE, 2022).

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